

ROUTES OF DAILY PRACTICES: FOOD, CLOTHING AND LINGUISTIC CHOICES IN THE STUDY OF PLURALISM IN PRE-MODERN MEDITERRANEAN PORT CITIES¹

FILOMENA VIVIANA TAGLIAFERRI

Istituto di Storia dell'Europa Mediterranea – CNR and University of Maryland-College Park

The aim of this article is to contribute to the rich and important Braudelian tradition in the study of the Mediterranean and how its One-Plural paradigm could be observed and analysed in daily behaviours involving tendencies towards the hybridisation and differentiation of foreign groups and individual material practices in different pre-modern Mediterranean port cities. After providing an overview of how scholarship has questioned the issue of the conceptual unity of the Mediterranean, the article focuses on the employment of material practices in the historical inquiry as a tool for highlighting meaningful behaviour in cultural identity's negotiation and affirmation in plural environments. The aim is to expound how a comparison of the combination of these identitarian visual expressions in distant Mediterranean urban environments linked by maritime routes offers meaningful insights into how the political context, and not a global Mediterranean attitude, served to shape specific answers to the problem of cultural pluralism.

Keywords: Braudel, Mediterraneanism, One-Plural, travel literature, material practices, pluralism, port cities.

In the beginning was Braudel. This could be the extreme synthesis of the genesis of the *Mare Nostrum* as a field of study for historians, scholars of other disciplines and the perception of erudite western society generally. In fact, the contribution of Fernand Braudel's two-volume masterpiece was so exceptional that he became the ultimate point of reference for anyone, from *La Méditerranée* onwards (1949), wishing to inquire into any aspect of Mediterranean history. This unconditional statement is easily proven merely by scanning the introductions of books and articles — including this one — on the subject. Braudel not only set the terms of the discussion. He also inaugurated what is likely the greatest debate in this regard, that is, the challenge of the conceptual unity of the Mediterranean. Is the Mediterranean space a unified entity, a unique geographical and cultural *koinè* embracing all the varieties found along its shores and on its islands? Does a Mediterranean way of being exist as a common frame merging the social, historical and anthropological models of all Mediterranean societies? Is the tendency towards hybridisation of Mediterranean environments inevitable *tout court*, or is it impossible to reduce all the cultural components present in the area to a single definition? Drawing on Braudel, scholars have confronted the key issue of Mediterranean societies' tendencies towards unity or fragmentation.

This essay aims to contribute to this rich, important tradition and to offer new insight into how this One-Plural paradigm — the ever-movable balance between *one* Mediterranean and *several* Mediterranean-s — could be observed and analysed from a

privileged point of view, that is, in daily behaviours that tend to hybridise and differentiate foreign groups and individual material practices in different pre-modern Mediterranean contact zones of port cities. This article will initially provide an overview of how scholarship on the Mediterranean has questioned the issue of ‘unity’, before moving on to the matter of how scholars have employed material practices in the historical determination of the balance of acculturation. I contend that material practices constitute a privileged point of access to the dynamic of identity affirmation in plural environments.

I will call upon two specific moments of historiographic synthesis — firstly on post-Braudelian Mediterranean literature, and secondly on studies focusing on food, clothing and language — to identify problems linked to the study of Mediterranean pre-modern identity. They are the basis on which I will develop the methodological approach deemed most suitable for framing and interpreting pre-modern sources in the study of Mediterranean cultural identities. Purposefully omitting a specific case study (and related primary sources), the proposed approach could help scholars better understand pre-modern cultural dynamics, supported by examples from existing scholarly works.

My ultimate aim is to advocate that a comparative analysis of daily practices in different and distant Mediterranean environments is the most appropriate method for inquiring into the One-Plural issue. Indeed, by comparing all these identitarian visual expressions in different and distant Mediterranean urban environments linked by maritime routes, I intend to offer a valuable insight into how political context, rather than a global Mediterranean attitude, shaped specific answers to the problem of cultural pluralism. Ultimately, I support the crucial role of the political factor in determining the balance of acculturation in the pre-modern Mediterranean space.

The One-Plural Issue and the Nature of the Mediterranean Space

As has already been pointed out in recent scholarship, Braudel’s established status as a founding father proved quite restrictive for advances in historical research on ‘the Mediterranean’, establishing him as a solitary navigator (Marino 2010: 3; Dursteler 2011: 416). In fact, for almost fifty years historians delivered no significant responses when enquiring into the topic, and if Braudel’s success was not accompanied by the advent of a generation of scholars in the field, this was partly due to Braudel’s legacy itself. Awe, reverence and the difficulty of managing such a vast territory as the Braudellian one discouraged historians from engaging with the subject for decades (Horden & Purcell 2000: 39–41). Practically speaking, Braudel ruled out the Mediterranean as a feasible historical category at the same time as generating it (Dursteler 2010: 65–69), simultaneously obliging anyone wishing to engage with the field to confront the crucial problem of its unity.

The first scholars forced to challenge this issue were not historians but anthropologists. In fact, while awaiting a resurrection of the field — which occurred in 2000 with the publication of *The Corrupting Sea* — the empty space left by historians was occupied by a new anthropology (Albera 2006; Dursteler 2011: 416), mainly by anglophone scholars. This trend enjoyed a discreet success during the 1960s and 1970s before declining in the 1980s after the legitimacy of its methodological approach was severely criticised, especially when based on a regional comparison (according to the similarity of Mediterranean spaces and the contrast with northern European ones)

(Herzfeld 1980). Once again, the issue of the conceptual unity of the Mediterranean came to the fore. It was challenged for two main reasons. The first was linked to the risk of the amalgamation of a rich cultural diversity by an a-priori assumption of the unity of the Mediterranean space. The second was the challenge of the Mediterranean as a subject of analysis. The category itself was denounced as a non-neutral construction by Anglo-Saxon academics, who applied an Orientalistic-like approach and vision to the study of southern European countries, creating a space between their academic authority and their subject of study, a Foucauldian discourse of power on Mediterranean environments. Michael Herzfeld denounced this 'Mediterraneanism' as a dangerous intellectual practice that, through the hardening of categories, had led to the exoticisation of the Mediterranean (Bromberger 2006) and to a stereotyped and ethnocentric view of southern Europe that — by comparison — implicitly exalted the values of the 'virtuous' Northerners and justified the economic and cultural subordination of the South itself (Herzfeld 1984: 443).

The rise and decline of this anthropological approach were both crucial to the ascent of a 'new', scholarly Mediterranean, far more centred on the use of the epistemological category of the Mediterranean as a series of ideologically constructed spaces. Ultimately, anthropology served as a fresh theoretical base for those historians that, in the last decade of the twentieth century, had again begun to be attracted by the Mediterranean (Albera 2006: 122). This trend reached its peak with *The Corrupting Sea*, which inaugurated the renaissance of Mediterranean studies that have since continued to flourish and are a focal point of academic interest. What is crucial here is that Peregrine Horden and Nicholas Purcell's narrative re-introduced the discussion of the One-Plural nature that has subsequently been problematised and applied to a variety of scholarly analyses, which still question Mediterranean unicity as a subject of inquiry. The two authors' methodological reflections on the history of the Mediterranean compared to histories in the Mediterranean could be connected to two essential questions, both of which address the consistency and legitimacy of this field of study. Firstly, can the Mediterranean be reduced to a thing, a 'real' Mediterranean identity that would allow us to trace a common trend in Mediterranean historical cultures? And secondly, why do we study the Mediterranean and how can we avoid the risk of essentialism and reductionism of the 'one-thing' approach and its use in a non-neutral hegemonic context?

The second question, concerning 'legitimacy', might find its answer in the way in which the new approach to the Mare Nostrum combines anthropology and other social sciences in historical analysis.² Theories are a source of inspiration for historians, in line with Peter Burke's promotion of more integration between theoretical and historical practices (Burke 2005: 188–189). Following this idea, the reason a theoretical approach is favoured over other possible approaches when studying the Mediterranean is that it makes the latter 'say something' about the present, which indicates that studying the Mediterranean often derives from an ethical choice.

The answer to the One-Plural issue, however, is far more complex and could arguably be resumed thus: due to its physical reality, it is not possible to reduce the eternal swinging of the Mediterranean between the One and the Plural. While it is a truism that the sea both divides and connects, this makes it no less true: the Mediterranean space is characterised both by its exceptional connectivity and by its fragmentation, representing a highly compartmental area (Bresson 2005: 95) where 'the relative proximity of opposite shores,

but the clear separation between shores, enables different cultures to interact with one another across what may at times seem almost impermeable cultural barriers' (Abulafia 2005: 92). This closeness and ease of contact make the Mediterranean a valuable subject of inquiry thanks to the richness of the different 'microecologies' and their interconnections (Horden 2005: 29).³ Given its peculiarity as a trans-cultural and trans-national space, groups can easily enter into contact and communicate with one another, sharing historical elements and events and being subject to the same geographical, political and economic influences. It is a border-space in which cultures are not opposed but overlap — influencing each other (Herzfeld 2001: 142; Darling 2012) — and whose different parts constantly renegotiate their boundaries and identities (Molho 2003). Identities (of whatever nature) are indeed the core of the One-Plural issue. Historians of the Mediterranean — influenced by post-modern and post-Orientalistic discourse, anthropology and the related historical approaches — have taken premodern identity to be a dynamic process, something fluid, renegotiated, involving a continuous movement through the porous barriers between the self and other due to daily contiguity and contact (Greene 2000; Dursteler 2006; Trivellato 2009; Rothman 2012). In such works, scholars tend to consider identity as the 'social positioning of self and other' (Bucholtz & Hall 2005: 586; Molinelli 2017: 1) as it is realised in specific historical and cultural settings, a process that allows individuals and groups to identify and/or self-identify with other individuals and groups that partake in social interaction along with them (Brubaker & Frederick 2000; Hall 2000). Thus, referring to the One-Plural issue, privileging the representation of identities as similar or unique appears to be an Aristotelian contingent predicate (in the sense of *ενδεχόμενον*) rather than a Kantian immanent one. The choice of narrators — both the authors of the sources and the historians analysing them — is 'the' crucial element in determining the balance between the uniformity and/or difference of Mediterranean historical cultures. The connectivity-fragmentation paradigm acts as an irreducible multiplicity in contact zones (Trim De Souza 2006: 79), giving pre-modern identity an inclusive nature, as the adoption of one identity does not exclude participation in another or others (Tagliaferri 2016: 107). This 'irreducibility' not only lies in archival and historical narrations but also informs the reality of the Mediterranean border space itself, where coexistence and conflict are both true and determined by historical circumstances, a balance dependent on the different historical policies that have governed the Mediterranean zone. Practically speaking, in the early modern Mediterranean, conflict or coexistence were decided either by Ottoman pragmatic policies or by European confessionalist ones. The irreducibility of cultural oppositions in such contact places is also supported by the anthropological and sociological discourse suggesting that we can never speak of impermeable societies along borders. In this sense, I agree with Hannerz's criticism of the epistemological approach, according to which cultures and identities can be said to resemble animals and plants, and are treated as bounded entities that 'have probably never [...] existed for any great length of time' (Herzfeld 2001: 137). Historical reality is far more open to flows and influences.

In this context, I wish to highlight the role of the political element in determining differences in the One-Plural balance so as to understand how this contributes to the creation of diverse border spaces from the same groups, a key element in the elaboration of coexistence strategies. The crucial role of the political factor in determining the quality

of border-space cities appears to have been neglected in favour of an emphasis on economic dynamics. Quality is intended here as those elements that determine the nature, kind and character of the city.⁴ Different policies have nonetheless shaped different approaches to the management of pluralism in contact zones, occasionally accentuating common traits or leading to the dominance of a Freudian ‘narcissism of small differences’, a concept Anton Blok re-employs to describe a situation where the other becomes so close as to be intolerable, generating the need to exacerbate differences (Bromberger 2006: 103).

Penetrating the One-Plural Issue: the Key Role of Diverse Political Managements in Determining the Materiality of Identity

To understand how the One-Plural nature of the Mediterranean functioned in specific historical periods, I propose a methodology focused on how different Mediterranean urban spaces contributed to the genesis of different, synchronic, and plural societies. In other words, I offer a comparative overview of urban environments in the premodern Mediterranean to better understand how political authorities influenced the type of integration/differentiation of foreign communities in Mediterranean port cities. A similar approach has already been employed in research on the behaviour of trading diasporas (Cohen 1971: 267; Van Gelder 2009: 13), focusing on how the urban space is influenced and influences the genesis of a plural society. The nature of the city as a built environment (Herzfeld 2001: 133) with its own rules and rhythms is crucial for its definition as a subject of epistemological enquiry — even though the city-inland opposition is often more symbolic than real (Driessen 2005: 130–131). The economic dynamics of cities encourage consumption and production, while attracting different kinds of groups that might find a space for unexplored opportunities. However, I would suggest that cities should not be considered as non-places because they were determined, crucially, by the particular administration policies of their states. Returning to the One-Plural issue, Mediterranean entrepôts are both similar and diverse, allowing us to follow both the story *of* our sea and the stories *in* our sea.

Mediterranean port cities constitute a useful point of observation as they create a privileged environment where different groups were more likely to meet, leading historians to

be tempted to say [...] that the essential Mediterranean race is that which inhabits its extravagant cosmopolitan ports [...] a single race embracing all others. But this is patently absurd (Braudel 1972–1973: 763).

Historians have often studied and grouped Mediterranean port cities, deeming them cognate enough to build meaningful comparisons (Driessen 2005; Eldem, Goffman & Masters 2005; Giaccaria 2012; Grenet 2016; Tagliaferri 2018). Indeed, the use of the category of the Mediterranean port city implies the existence of common traits (a ‘unity’). Such traits make them ‘inquirable’ in relation to similar aspects, notably the presence of the same cultural groups, and the high level of exchange between such cities through maritime routes. In other words, their *trait d’union* lies in their similar cultural pluralism, marked interconnectivity and shared history, in a fascinating net of

multicultural routes. The question of shared history is arguably what determines a tangible similarity in the establishment of a Mediterranean way of being.

On the other hand, the way in which the political and physical differences of specific cities influenced the kind of pluralism they developed demonstrates how specific places played ‘the’ crucial role in determining the quality of a city. This is what renders the multiple Mediterranean experiences irreducible to a supra one, since state policies heavily influence the way in which individuals build relationships with diversity and the expression of cultural identity (Tagliaferri 2018: 207).

The category of the Mediterranean port city is therefore useful for researching the complexity of the Mediterranean itself, a complexity that might be better expressed through the comparison of distant Mediterranean environments and the multiple combinations in which the same phenomena occurred over history. Through a comparison of distant environments, we not only go beyond overly localised approaches but also overcome the difficulties presented by the analysis of polysemantic spaces such as the Mediterranean. This less localised approach allows for a more ‘articulate access to phenomena which, duly problematized, are characteristic throughout the region’ (Tagliaferri 2018: 6).

Even if Braudel’s ‘extravagant cosmopolitan ports’ are not of one kind only and do not exemplify the larger Mediterranean system, they offer a unique point of access for studying its culture contacts and cultural plurality (Reyerson & Watkins 2014). This is also because the cities’ ‘circumscribe-ness’ concentrates the diverse practices (and people) spread along the sea shores, magnifying social and cultural experiences and pluralising them.⁵ In fact, as already pointed out by scholars, premodern Mediterranean cities cannot be labelled as either cosmopolitan or multicultural. The multicultural milieu implies an investment in the value of a universal society where particularisms are unified under a supra-comprehensive cultural entity. In privileging universalism, the multiculturalist approach tends to exclude different cultures and individuals (Parens 1994) in a context in which hybridisation can only occur through the incorporation of different elements into a blurred *mestizaje* (Hernández 1993). On the other hand, cosmopolitanism is ‘elitist in formulation and content’ (Giaccaria 2012: 298), deriving from the concept of the Mediterranean as a post-colonial sea, where the European Self is confronted with a Mediterranean Other who has fallen from the classical state of grace and expresses an imperial and colonial ideology (Giaccaria 2012: 299). Built on the oxymoronic tension between *cosmos* (universal) and *polis* (particular), cosmopolitanism expresses the desire for identity of an urban ruling class of non-endogamic origins exposed to different cultural influences. Cosmopolitanism is the opposite of the federalism and homogeneity proper to the multicultural formulation; it is a *pensée de midi* often expressed by international intellectuals and their work (Lekatsas 2014). Premodern Mediterranean port cities were different. They were plural spaces where communities lived next to one another, maintaining their specific characteristics and entering into a system that recognised them as diverse (Smyrnelis 2006; Tagliaferri 2018: 121–122). The role of the city in privileging the coexistence of more than one cultural group seems to be supported by the simple factual observation that

of all types of settlement, it is the town or the city where one is most likely to encounter a stranger or foreigner [...] often originated from afar and [...] distinguished by language,

physical appearance, dress, beliefs or practices, characteristics covered by the slippery modern terms ‘ethnicity’ of ‘cultural identity’ (Keene 2016: 1).

The visibility of the stranger was central to configuring the urban settlement, often determined by the state authorities’ expectation of recognisability, a visibility that involved the reproduction of sets of material practices that shaped daily life.

This is arguably the key point in approaching the Mediterranean One-Plural problem in relation to the city. When examining how pluralism affected urban life and how culture contacts affected the expression of identity, an analysis of material practices offers a privileged means of enquiring into the city’s new dwellers’ negotiation of two opposing attitudes: namely, the desire to maintain practices from their place of origin, and acculturation to those of their new environment. These attitudes should both be considered as strategies employed by groups and individuals to reaffirm their perceived identity and as a way of reacting creatively to new environments, drawing upon their own cultural backgrounds.

Here and from this point on, identity is primarily intended as ‘a way of being and doing’ (Jansen 2001: 208), that is, a way of making things in everyday life involving material practices. The concreteness of this aspect of identity leads individuals to self-position themselves in relation to other individuals who are recognised as similar or different according to how they do things. This is particularly meaningful when examining pre-modern Mediterranean pluralisms.

The materiality of identity should not be seen as a ‘folklorisation’ of historical knowledge. Rather, from Daniel Roche’s perspective, it is to be understood as a focus on ‘re-materialising the principles of our knowledge and so achieving a better grasp of our relation to things, our mediation with objects and the world around us’ (Roche 2000: 1–2). The use of material practices as identity detectors sheds light on the possible ways in which identity has been channelled in the visible forms of daily life. This kind of materiality as concrete identity not only allows us to study what a specific cultural group saw as meaningful, but also highlights how historical negotiations of identity were subject to material constraints, being highly dependent on the availability of certain products in the place of arrival.

Daily practices and material life have been studied using different types of sources. To examine the One-Plural issue, I propose a comparative study of travellers’ accounts of the time — where groups’ behaviours can be more easily identified — alongside archival sources — in which individual attitudes toward acculturation and isolation are more readily apparent. The use of travel accounts in cultural studies has been greatly problematised, as travellers have been often theorised as the forerunners of an Orientalistic-like discourse on otherness — an accusation deriving from the well-known analysis of travel literature developed in Edward Said’s *Orientalism* (1978). However, this approach has been contested in recent literature, which has highlighted the ability of many premodern travellers to approach diversity (Roddan 2016; Harper 2011: 2; Ghobrial 2014: 3, 8). I would posit that travel narratives often constituted an attempt at cultural synthesis. By this, I mean that individual foreigners often attempted to recompose plural cities into a unity, assigning each group a role within the urban economy. Sometimes, they allow for a sense of the functionality of multicultural policies in enhancing urban welfare in early modern writers’ perceptions, as the port cities of the Mediterranean were

‘expected’ to constitute a small-scale representation of the vaster world, to concentrate the wider *kosmos* in the *polis*. The ‘foreigner focus’ (Freller 2009: 1–50) was often driven by an identification of the ‘rules’ governing the urban social space, leading authors to focus more on the differences between groups rather than their similarities. This attitude to taxonomy is counterbalanced by travellers’ many observations on private encounters with concrete Others potentially displaying different degrees of acculturation, adopting — either by choice or due to circumstances — some of the host culture’s behavioural patterns and/or values (Fox 2004: 17). Travel accounts retain a real anthropological value, as a tool whose cross-use could help support the less abundant and descriptive information in archival sources. From the late seventeenth century onward, travel narratives were supported — at least theoretically — by the precise practice of only reporting reliable information (Armstrong 2005; Tagliaferri 2014), which enhanced their value as historical and ethnographic sources.

To examine how identity, as a way of doing things materially, is negotiated in premodern port cities, I will focus on three identity markers: food, clothing and language. Both food and clothing have long been the primary subjects of anthropological observation (Mauss 2017: 41–56), while language — a major vehicle of cultural transmission — has only recently been recognised in its materiality (Bleich 2013).

Identity as a Way of Making Things: Eating, Dressing and Speaking and the Expression of ‘Strangeness’

Through my discussion of these three markers, which is by no means exhaustive, I intend to propose a summary of their possible uses in the type of historiographical analysis promoted here — that is, the study of identities. I will again focus on existing literature, my objective being to provide a picture of their potential to generate a multi-faceted depiction of urban pluralism, that is, a much more articulate image of the visibility of foreigners in cities than could be achieved by focusing on just one. I do not intend to engage in a deep inquiry into how foreigners ate, dressed or spoke. Rather, I will examine how they employed this set of visible practices to channel and express their (original or acquired) cultural belonging.

As a subject of historical inquiry, foodways began to attract scholars’ attention in the 1980s, but have only recently become a fashionable topic, especially for the Mediterranean. In this case, the historical shift towards the study of social and cultural aspects of daily life went hand in hand with the long-lasting regard for the so-called Mediterranean in anglo-phone countries, a concept developed in a non-Mediterranean context. Mediterranean cuisine implies the style — in its many regional expressions — of combining products from Mediterranean lands, that is, using the same raw materials with different handling procedures or the same procedures for different ingredients. Elizabeth David’s *A Book of Mediterranean Food* (1950) was a milestone in the affirmation of this concept.⁶ The conceptualisation of a common eating style in the Mediterranean space is echoed in Braudel’s work, as his stress on the geophysical similarity of the coastal areas and attention to the circulation of products and techniques led him to underscore the similarity between Mediterranean foodways (Braudel 1972–1973: 237). This similarity has, however, been greatly problematised by recent scholarship on the topic, in a kind of culinary version of the One-Plural dilemma (Grieco

1996; Wright 1999; Teti 1999). Such works have developed along two primary research lines. Firstly, they have analysed the sense of unfamiliarity and unease of travellers moving around the Mediterranean when approaching local foods (Dursteler 2012; Dursteler 2014). And secondly, they have examined how food has been used to mark identitarian belonging, often of a religious nature (Freidenreich 2011; Villani 2018). These works reflect an anthropological approach to the study of what humans eat, considering taste as a socially constructed normative system of cultural practices, interiorised in the human biological system, which reproduces itself (Fischler 1985: 171–172), as ‘la nourriture ne doit pas seulement être bonne à manger, elle doit être bonne à penser’ (Lévi-Strauss 2008 [1961]: 533). More recent approaches have supported a much looser relationship between food and the construction of identity, which is seen mainly as a cultural identification and less in structuralist terms (Scholliers 2001). From this perspective, considerable emphasis has been placed on the meaning of eating together, based on norms around the selection of eating partners, that is, commensality both as a gathering aimed at satisfying a material need and as a symbolic obligation of a collective nature (Grignon 2001). This attention to the creation of ritualised moments when social groups share food is particularly crucial when studying groups of foreigners in new environments since food re-knots community bonds together. Foodways preserve groups’ identities in the diaspora, constituting a defence against the acculturation of the space of arrival, as in the case of the Jews (Douglas 1966: 37) or, more recently, of Italian emigrants in the United States (Cinotto 2013). Commensality sheds light on who was considered as a desirable eating partner in Mediterranean ports as well as on the existing (or emerging) social networks to which eaters belonged.

Daniel Roche’s *The Culture of Clothing* marked a turning point in the study of clothing in historical scholarship. Clothing is ‘another of the ways in which people convert nature into culture’ (Herzfeld 2001: 139); it is a global social fact in Marcel Mauss’ sense (Roche 1989: 512). In pre-modern societies based on social and cultural orders, appearance was expected to reveal both social and cultural affiliations. This imperative was to be subverted only in ritually-charged contexts, such as the Carnival; otherwise, it always had been possible to judge a book by its cover, in a perfect match between belonging and appearance.

Concerning the One-Plural issue, the obsession with identification through clothing was particularly noticeable in places of culture contact. Ottoman and European laws sought to prohibit the use of Ottoman clothing by Europeans travelling or living in the Ottoman Empire (Ricci 2002: 173–192; Ricci, 2008: 105–141), while Catholic missionaries were unfavourably impressed by the close similarity of the male-female and rich-poor Ottoman dress codes (Heyberger 2009: 311), ambiguity of appearance being seen as an expression of ambiguity in personal ethics.

The anthropological quality of clothing as a general system, as well as dressing as an individual act (Roche 1989: 45–46), makes it particularly appropriate for studying the oscillation between the hybridisation and isolation of foreigners in pre-modern port cities. This is central to Ricca’s dilemma in Montesquieu’s *Persian Letters*, when he presents himself in society for the first time in European dress: if I am not dressed as a Persian, am I still Persian? (Montesquieu 2008 [1721]: 40).

Travellers and collections of clothing illustrations both suggest very neat social and cultural divisions, expressed through a display of clothes that creates ‘types’. The collections, in particular, ‘create an impression and established a difference, but they also revealed what was expected’, contributing to ‘the creation of a discourse on otherness’ (Roche 1989: 11). One such collection, *Gli abiti de’ veneziani, di quasi ogni età*, by Giovanni Grevembroch (1754), is of particular interest for our study of foreign groups in port cities because the author — a painter born into a Netherlandish family in Venice in 1731 — portrayed not only the representatives of each merchant group conducting business in the Laguna but also foreign dwellers of the city — mainly migrants from Greek and Jewish communities.⁷ One of his tables contains a useful example of resistance versus acculturation tendencies in the clothing habits of Greek women in Venice, seemingly influenced by marital status and place of origin. The *Sfachiotta* table (Figure 1) shows a young woman from Sfakià, in the region of Chanià, Crete. Sfakian girls came to work in patrician houses because of their abilities as domestic servants and she is depicted here in traditional Cretan dress.

Figure 1. *Sfachiotta*.

in the Venetian fashion, mostly in black, but keeping a white headscarf over their head and shoulders’ (1981 [1754]: 71). The exchange of dress codes in Mediterranean contact zones — often led by women — would eventually represent a laboratory in the divorce between being and seeming and the erosion of ideological borders in the generation of fashion trends where individuality of choice would be central (Inal 2011).

On the last of our identity markers — language behaviour — historians have largely employed socio-linguistic tools for some time now, based on the observation that ‘the language system of a given culture, like its culinary system, its vestimentary system [...], reflects the whole culture’ (Burke 1987: 13). According to the structuralist idea — first theorised by De Saussure — and Chomskian formalism, language exists independently of its speakers. This approach has been called into question in more recent sociolinguistic theories focusing on the agency of the speaker and on the non-neutrality and abstractness of language, making it ‘strictly connected to ideologies and power relationships’ (Consani & Cuzzolin 2017: 33) When approaching the study of language usage, it is important to highlight ‘who speaks what language to whom and when’ (Burke 1987: 3). In the case of language contact, that is, the case to which the One-Plural issue refers, the varieties of

However, in the description of the *Donna Greca* table (Figure 2), we find: ‘married Greek ladies here wear clothes, and ornaments, in the

Figure 2. *Donna Greca*.

linguistic choices, code-switching and the identitarian use of language need to be carefully evaluated, especially in a historical inquiry, where we are considerably limited by no longer having access to oral forms of communication. More specifically, the Mediterranean contact zone has been defined linguistically in terms of a ‘community of practice’, rather than a language community (Di Salvo, Mori & Muru 2017; Wenger 1998). The community of practice is characterised by an instrumental use of language, mainly oriented towards effective communication between non-homogeneous speakers. In a historical context, Dursteler has argued that, especially in ethnically composite empires, the use of language was linked not only to the expression of the speaker’s identity but also to their communication needs. In this sense, ‘language was a marker of identity but not of exclusion of other elements’ (Dursteler 2012: 77). Nevertheless, it is crucial to underline, firstly, that the Mediterranean cannot be treated as a community of practice in its entirety, and secondly that not all city dwellers can be equally considered as proficient members of the community. In fact, the Mediterranean space is not equally connected and many areas are more isolated than others, not to mention individual linguistic skills and education. From this perspective, being part of a polyglot empire did not automatically grant inter-linguistic skills. As for city dwellers, the capacity to switch between languages also needs to be connected to other factors, such as social class and gender (Pavlenko 2001). What seems crucial in determining the identitarian use of language is the speaker’s decision to use a specific code, through which he/she decides to identify him/herself and allows others to culturally classify him/her (Consani & Cuzzolin 2017: 44). This culturally motivated code-switching is ‘identity oriented’ (Turchetta 2017: 303). This is the case, for example, for Mihale/Catterina Šatorović, who appealed to the Venetian state authority to escape an arranged marriage organised by her father. When she met him again in Venice in 1627, more than five years after fleeing home, she was keen to speak to him only in Italian, through an interpreter, rather than in Turkish or Slavic, ‘using language to demarcate the boundary between the two of them.’ Only after several encounters did she decide to re-establish a sense of familiarity by asking him, in Slavic, ‘Father, do you love me?’, an extraordinary and touching example of culturally/emotionally motivated code-switching (Dursteler 2011: 73).

Returning to my methodological proposal, when applied to different port cities this set of identity markers offers an alternative, intriguing lens for examining the One-Plural paradigm, together with the possible ways in which cultural pluralism may have come to life over history along the early modern Mediterranean shores. Political authority is decisive at this juncture. Real cities were adjustable frames for pre-modern mindsets and for how the expression of ‘strangeness’ came about: the adapting strategies of foreigners were crucially conditioned by the state’s attitude towards otherness. We can see how this process occurred by comparing the two very different Mediterranean ports of Izmir and Valletta; such a comparison reveals how cultural pluralism was ‘interpreted’ differently in the two maritime environments (Tagliaferri 2018: 5; 207). In other words, it demonstrates how political authority determined the form cultural pluralism took in the city. In an Ottoman port city such as Izmir, cultural difference was granted visibility.

[here] we seem to be in Christendom; they speak nothing but Italian, French, English or Dutch there. Everybody takes off his Hat, when he pays his respects to another. There one sees Capuchins, Jesuits, Recolets [...] They sing publicly in the Churches [...] and perform Divine Service there without any trouble [...] Taverns are open all Hours, Day and Night (Pitton de Tournefort 1718: 336).

In the Ottoman empire, which employed pragmatic tolerance as a governing tool, minorities were free and forced to live next to one another, a condition favouring the expression of diversity and a clear division between groups. On the other hand, even if a city like Valletta, the capital of the Maltese state, attracted a vast, variegated category of foreigners, the expression of diversity occurred only at the two extremes of the social scale there, that is, for the knights of the Order of Saint John of Jerusalem and Muslim slaves. In Valletta, the acculturation process principally involved the lower strata of migrants (the majority of whom were male), who moved to Malta individually and entered a comprehensive Maltese lifestyle that could easily integrate foreigners (Cassar 2009: 54), displaying a kind of cosmopolitanism of assimilation according to which to become Maltese it was necessary merely to marry a Maltese woman (Mercieca 2000) and to be a Catholic (at least formally). In turn, however, this Maltese lifestyle (which included ways of eating, dressing and speaking) was heavily — and inevitably — influenced by the numerous foreigners that moved to the Grand Harbour area.

Conclusions

The material choices of foreigners in port cities shed great light on how they constructed cultural hierarchies, which is useful for mapping and lending order to diversity, determining the balance between the hybridisation and diversification of urban identities. These choices could be seen as strategies — sometimes varying greatly amongst themselves and over time (Van Gelder 2009: 131–168) — through which groups and individuals expressed their cultural belonging. On the other hand, the urban political context — rather than a global Mediterranean attitude — played a crucial role in determining the type of pluralism that developed. The new city users introduced not only external cultural elements but also new demands into the urban discourse (Sassen 2000: 91), stimulating the responsiveness of entities entrusted with organising geographical and social spaces. In the different port cities, this interaction between foreigners and authorities generated different forms of pre-modern pluralism that represent an incredibly fertile ground for scholars. In linking and comparing them along the multiple maritime routes that connect the urban realities of the Mediterranean Sea, a net of routes of daily practices could be established, again One and Plural, which is significant for understanding historical responses to cultural coexistence.

Notes

The author would like to thank Dr. Umberto Grassi for his precious advice in reviewing the article.

1. The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 747030 — MedRoute.

2. In Michael Herzfeld's words 'anthropology and history have danced a flirtatious pas de deux throughout the past century' (2001: 55).
3. The concept of connectivity is derived from the graph theory.
4. According to one of the Oxford English Dictionary's definitions of 'quality': 'restricted to cases in which there is comparison (expressed or implied) with other things of the same kind.'
5. Pre-modern cosmopolitanism could be seen as a set of plural practices (Grenet 2016).
6. Mediterranean diet, instead, was developed by doctor Ancel Keys (1959).
7. The Greeks were the most numerous foreign community of Venice, while in Venice the Jews found one of their most prestigious and long-lasting settlements in the Italian peninsula.

References

- Abulafia, D. 2005. Mediterraneans. In *Rethinking the Mediterranean*, (ed.) William V. Harris, Oxford: Oxford University Press 64–93.
- Albera, D. 2006. Anthropology of the Mediterranean: Between Crisis and Renewal. *History and Anthropology* **17(2)**: 109–133.
- Armstrong, C.D. 2005. Travel and Experience in the Mediterranean of Louis XV. In *Rethinking the Mediterranean*, (ed.) William V. Harris, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 235–267.
- Bleich, D. 2013. *The Materiality of Language: Gender, Politics, and the University*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Braudel, F. 1946. *La Méditerranée et le monde méditerranéen à l'époque de Philippe II*, 3 vols. Paris: Armand Colin. English version: Braudel, F. 1972–1973. *The Mediterranean and the Mediterranean World in the Age of Philip II*, 2 vols. New York: Harper & Row.
- Bresson, A. 2005. Ecology and Beyond: The Mediterranean Paradigm. In *Rethinking the Mediterranean*, (ed.) William V. Harris. Oxford: Oxford University Press 94–114.
- Bromberger, C. 2006. Towards an Anthropology of the Mediterranean. *History and Anthropology* **17(2)**: 98–99.
- Brubaker, R. & Cooper, F. 2000. Beyond 'identity'. *Theory and Society* **29**:1–47.
- Bucholtz, M & Hall, K. 2005. Identity and Interaction: A Socio-cultural Linguistic Approach. *Discourse Studies* **7(4-5)**: 585–614.
- Burke, P. 1987. Introduction. In *The Social History of the Language*, (eds) Peter Burke & Roy Porter, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1–19.
- 2005. *History and Social Theory*. Ithaca: Cornell (second edition).
- Cassar, C. 2009. Clothes, status and class in Malta under the Order of St John. *Sacra Militia* **8**: 15–20.
- Cinotto, S. 2013. *The Italian American Table: Food, Family, and Community in New York City*. Urbana, Chicago, Springfield: University of Illinois Press.
- Cohen, A. 1971. Cultural strategies in the organization of trading diasporas. In *The Development of Indigenous Trade and Markets in West Africa*, (ed.) Claude Meillassoux, Oxford: Oxford University Press 266–281.
- Consani, C. & Cuzzolin, P. 2017. Identity in Speakers' Discourse. In *Language and Identity in Multilingual Mediterranean Settings. Challenges for Historical Sociolinguistics*, (ed.) Piera Molinelli, Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton, 33–48.
- Darling, L. 2012. The Mediterranean as a Borderland *Review of Middle East Studies* **46(2)**: 54–63.
- David, E. 1950. *A Book of Mediterranean Food*. London: John Lehmann.
- Di Salvo, M.; Mori L. & Muru, C. 2017. The Mediterranean Community of Practices between Speaking and Writing in Early Modern Documents. In *Language and Identity in Multilingual Mediterranean Settings. Challenges for Historical Sociolinguistics*, (ed.) Piera Molinelli, Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton 309–324.

- Douglas, M. 1966. *Purity and Danger: An Analysis of Concepts of Pollution and Taboo*. London: Routledge and Keegan Paul.
- Driessen, H. 2005. Mediterranean port cities: Cosmopolitanism reconsidered. *History and Anthropology* **16**(1): 129–141.
- Dursteler, E. R. 2006. *Venetians in Constantinople: Nation, Identity, and Coexistence in the Early Modern Mediterranean*. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- 2010. Fernand Braudel (1902–1985). In *French Historians 1900-2000: New Historical Writing in Twentieth-Century France*, (eds) P. Daileader & P. Whalen, Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell 62–76.
- 2011. On Bazaars and Battlefields: Recent Scholarship on Mediterranean Cultural Contacts. *Journal of Early Modern History* **15**: 413–434.
- 2011. *Renegade Women: Gender, Identity, and Boundaries in the Early Modern Mediterranean World*. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- 2012. Infidel Foods: Food and Identity in Early Modern Ottoman Travel Literature. *The Journal of Ottoman Studies* **39**: 143–160.
- 2012. Speaking in Tongues: Language and Communication in the Early Modern Mediterranean. *Past and Present* **217**: 47–77.
- 2014. Bad Bread and the ‘Outrageous Drunkenness of the Turks’: Food and Identity in the Accounts of Early Modern European Travelers to the Ottoman Empire. *Journal of World History* **25**(2-3): 203–228.
- Eldem, E.; Goffman, D. & Masters B. (eds) 2005. *The Ottoman City between East and West: Aleppo, Izmir, and Istanbul*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Fischler, C. 1985. Alimentation, cuisine et identité: l’identification des aliments et l’identité du mangeur. In *Identité alimentaire et altérité culturelle. Actes du Colloque de Neuchâtel, 12-13 novembre 1984*, Neuchâtel: Institut d’Ethnologie 171–192.
- Fox, K. 2004. *Watching the English: The Hidden Rules of English Behaviour*. London: Hodder and Stoughton.
- Freidenreich, D. M. 2011. *Foreigners and Their Food. Constructing Otherness in Jewish, Christian, and Islamic Law*. Berkley, Los Angeles, London: University of California Press.
- Freller, T. 2009. *Malta and the Grand Tour*. Malta: Midsea Books.
- Ghobrial, J. P. 2014. *The Whispers of Cities: Information Flows in Istanbul, London, and Paris in the Age of William Trumbull*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Giaccaria, P. 2012. Cosmopolitanism: The Mediterranean Archives. *The Geographical Review* **102**: 293–315.
- Greene, M. 2000. *A Shared World: Christians and Muslims in the Early Modern Mediterranean*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Grenet, M. 2016. *La fabrique communautaire. Les Grecs à Venise, Livourne et Marseille 1770–1840*. Roma: École de française de Rome.
- 2016. Villes, diasporas, cosmopolitisme(s): une perspective historique. *Diasporas. Circulation, migration, histoire* **28**: 55–63.
- Grevembroch, G. 1981 [1754]. *Gli abiti de’ veneziani, di quasi ogni età con diligenza raccolti, e dipinti nel secolo XVIII*, 4 vols. Venezia: Filippi Editore.
- Grignon, C. 2001. Commensality and Social Morphology: An Essay of Typology. In *Food, Drink and Identity: Cooking, Eating and Drinking in Europe since the Middle Age*, (ed.) Peter Scholliers, Oxford & New York: Berg 27–28.
- Grieco, A.G. 1996. ¿Cocina mediterránea o dieta mediterránea (del siglo XIV a principios del XVI)? In *La Alimentación mediterránea: historia, cultura, nutrición*, (ed.) Francisco Xavier Medina, Barcelona: Icaria Editorial 117–126.
- Hall, S. 2000. Who needs ‘identity’? In *Identity. A Reader*, (eds) Paul Du Gay, Jessica Evans & Peter Redman, London, Thousand Oaks and New Delhi: SAGE Publications 15–30.

- Harper, J.G. 2011. Introduction. In *The Turk and Islam in the Western Eye, 1450–1750: Visual Imagery before Orientalism*, (ed.) James G. Harper, Farnham: Ashgate 1–18.
- Hernández, F. 1993. From Multiculturalism to Mestizaje in World Culture. *Visual Arts Research* **19(2)**: 1–12.
- Herzfeld, M. 1980. Honour and shame: Problems in the comparative analysis of moral systems. *Man (NS)* **15**: 339–351.
- 1984. The horns of the Mediterraneanist dilemma. *American Ethnologist* **11(3)**: 439–454.
- 2001. *Anthropology. Theoretical Practice in Culture and Society*. Malden: Blackwell Publishers.
- Heyberger, B. 2009. L’Islam dei missionari cattolici (Medio Oriente, Seicento). In *(L’Islam visto da Occidente: Cultura e religione del Seicento europeo di fronte all’Islam, Atti del Convegno Internazionale (17–18 ottobre 2007))*, (eds) Bernard Heyberger *et al.*, Genova-Milano: Marietti 1820.
- Horden, P. 2005. Mediterranean excuses: Historical writing on the Mediterranean since Braudel. *History and Anthropology* **16(1)**: 25–30.
- Horden, P. & Purcell N. 2000. *The Corrupting Sea: A Study of Mediterranean History*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Inal, O. 2011. Women’s fashions in transition: Ottoman borderlands and the Anglo-Ottoman exchange of costumes. *Journal of World History* **22(2)**: 243–272.
- Jansen, W. 2001. French Bread and Algerian Wine: Conflicting Identities in French Algeria. In *Food, Drink and Identity: Cooking, Eating and Drinking in Europe since the Middle Age*, (ed.) Peter Scholliers, Oxford & New York: Berg 195–218.
- Keene, D. 2016. Segregation, Zoning and Assimilation in Medieval Towns. In *Segregation – Integration – Assimilation. Religious and Ethnic Groups in the Medieval Towns of Central and Eastern Europe*, (eds) Derek Keene, Balázs Nagy & Katalin Szende, Farnham: Ashgate 1–13.
- Keys, A. B. & Keys, M. 1959. *Eat Well and Stay Well*. New York: Doubleday.
- Lekatsas, B. 2014. La pensée de midi: Mediterranean Cosmopolitanism in the Work of Camus, Cavafy, and Chahine. *Journal of Comparative Poetics* **34**: 125–150.
- Lévi-Strauss, C. 2008 [1961]. Le totémisme aujourd’hui. In Claude Lévi-Strauss, *Ouvres*. Paris, Gallimard.
- Marino, J. 2010. Braudel’s Mediterranean and Italy. *California Italian Studies Journal* **1**: 1–19.
- Mauss, M. 2017 [1947]. *Manual of Ethnography*. New York & Oxford: Durkheim Press.
- Mercieca, S. 2000. Amicitia Extenditur ad Extraneos: Marriage Law and the Concept of Citizenship (1563–1789). *Journal of Mediterranean Studies* **10(1)**: 151–171.
- Molho, A. 2003. Il Mediterraneo. In *Pisa e il Mediterraneo. Uomini, merci, idee dagli Etruschi ai Medici*, (ed.) Marco Tangheroni, Milan: Skira 273–279.
- Molinelli, P. 2017. Linguistic Representations of Identity. Texts, Contexts, and Methods in Diachronic Perspective. In *Language and Identity in Multilingual Mediterranean Settings. Challenges for Historical Sociolinguistics*, (ed.) Piera Molinelli, Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton 1–30.
- Montesquieu, C. L. 2008 (1721). *Persian Letters*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Parens, J. 1994. Multiculturalism and the Problem of Particularism. *The American Political Science Review* **88(1)**: 169–181.
- Pavlenko, A. 2001. Bilingualism, gender, and ideology. *International Journal of Bilingualism* **5(2)**: 117–151.
- Pitton de Tournefort, J. 1718. *A voyage into the Levant, perform’d by command of the late French king*, 3 vols. London: D. Browne *et al.*
- Reyerson, K.L., Watkins, J. (eds.) 2014. *Mediterranean Identities in the Premodern Era: Entrepôts, Islands, Empires (Transculturalisms, 1400–1700)*. Farnham: Ashgate.

- Ricci, G. 2002. *Ossessione turca: in una retrovia cristiana dell'Europa moderna*. Bologna: Il Mulino 2002.
- 2008. *I Turchi alle porte*. Bologna: Il Mulino.
- Roche, D. 1989. *The Culture of Clothing. Dress and Fashion in the 'Ancien Régime'*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- 2000. *A History of Everyday Things: The Birth of Consumption in France, 1600–1800*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Roddan, H. 2016. 'Orientalism is a Partisan Book': Applying Edward Said's Insights to Early Modern Travel Writing. *History Compass* **14**(4): 168–188.
- Rothman, N.E. 2012. *Brokering Empire: Trans-Imperial Subjects between Venice and Istanbul*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Said, E. 1978. *Orientalism*. New York: Pantheon Books.
- Sassen, S. 2000. The Global City: Strategic Site/New Frontier. *American Studies* **41**: 79–95.
- Scholliers, P. 2001. Meals, Food Narratives, and Sentiments of Belonging in Past and Present. In *Food, Drink and Identity: Cooking, Eating and Drinking in Europe since the Middle Age*, (ed.) Peter Scholliers, Oxford & New York: Berg 3–22.
- Smyrnelis, M. C. 2006. *Une ville ottomane plurielle : Smyrne aux XVIIIe et XIXe siècles*. Istanbul: Éditions Isis.
- Tagliaferri, F.V. 2014. Subjects in between: three different ways of translating experience by Italian travellers in late 17th-early 18th century Ottoman space. *Cahiers de la Méditerranée* **88**(1): 329–351.
- 2016. In the Process of Being Levantines. The 'Levantinization' of the Catholic Community of Izmir (1683–1724). *Turkish Historical Review* **7**(1): 86–112.
- 2018. *Tolerance Re-Shaped in the Early-Modern Mediterranean Borderlands: Travellers, Missionaries and Proto-Journalists (1683–1724)*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Teti, V. 1999. *Il colore del cibo. Geografia, mito e realtà dell'alimentazione mediterranea*. Roma: Meltemi.
- Trim De Souza, R. 2006. Noi e gli altri. L'incontro tra culture come esperienza filosofico-antropologica. In *La frontiera mediterranea: tradizioni culturali e sviluppo locale*, (eds) Pietro Barcellona and Fabio Ciaramelli. Bari: Edizioni Dedalo 73–82.
- Trivellato, F. 2009. *The Familiarity of Strangers: The Sephardic Diaspora, Livorno, and Cross-Cultural Trade in the Early Modern Period*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Turchetta, B. 2017. The Writer's Identity and Identification Markers in Writing Code Mixing and Interference. In *Language and Identity in Multilingual Mediterranean Settings. Challenges for Historical Sociolinguistics*, (ed.) Piera Molinelli, Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton 291–308.
- Van Gelder, M. 2009. *Trading Places: The Netherlandish Merchants in Early Modern Venice*. Leiden & Boston: Brill.
- Villani, S. 2018. Unintentional Dissent. Eating: Meat and Religious Identity among British Residents in Early Modern Livorno. In *The Roman Inquisition: Centre versus Peripheries*, (eds) Katherine Aron-Beller and Christopher Black. Leiden: Brill 373–394.
- Wenger, E. 1998. *Community of Practices: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wright, C.A. 1999. *A Mediterranean Feast: The Story of the Birth of the Celebrated Cuisines of the Mediterranean, from the Merchants of Venice to the Barbary Corsairs; with More Than 500 Recipes*. New York: William Morrow Cookbooks.